

WIND MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS

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Abstract: In this scientific thesis, information and explanations about the group of Uzbek folk instruments are presented.

Key words: musical instrument, "Nay", "Koshnay", "Surnay", Bulamon, wind instruments.

Nay.

Another Uzbek folk instrument is the «Nay». The emergence of the «Nay» instrument also dates back to the ancient past. Uzbek folk instruments were formed in the embrace of ancient Eastern culture. They have preserved their unique characteristics and sound color during centuries of development. Pipes, trumpets, trumpets, trumpets and other wind instruments have come down to us in their traditional forms without changing their structure.

The «Nay» instrument is widespread not only in Uzbekistan and Tajikistan, but also in Buryatia, the Republic of Mongolia, and China. This instrument has different names in different countries. For example: in Uzbekistan and Tajikistan it is called nay, in Buryat and Mongolia it is called limba, and in China it is called li.

«Nay» musical instrument is played as a solo instrument, in ensembles and orchestras. Due to the wide range of the voice, he acts as a leader in folk tunes, statuses, and ensembles. According to its structure, it has six holes that can be closed with fingers, it has a diatonic sound range, and the total sound volume is from the first octave lya to the fourth octave re. Notes are written in treble clef. Full or half closing of the holes with fingers, half or full tonality. High and low sounds are produced by blowing in different ways. Between the hole for blowing the «Nay» and the first hole that is closed with the fingers, there is another hole to which a thin piece of paper is glued (this is mainly used in China). This method helps to make the sound waver. At the other end of the «Nay», four holes (two on both sides and the other two on the back), which are always open, serve to soften the sounds of some curtains. The total length of the pipe is 500-600 mm, it is made of wood, bail, reed and copper. Accordingly, it is called "Wooden pipe", "Copper pipe", "Gharov pipe". In recent years, a smaller version of the «Nay» has been used, and this small «Nay» is called "Piccola Nay". The sound of the «Nay» is very pleasant. This instrument is performed in two positions, i.e. sitting and standing. The «Nay» is tuned to the lye of a piano or wind instrument.

The deceased performers, who had a deep place in the hearts of Shinavandas with their skillful playing of the «Nay»: Abdugadir Ismailov, Saidjon Kalonov, Dadaali

Soatkulov, Jamil Kamolov, Isoq Kadirov, Mahmud Muhamedov, Rabbim Hamdamov, Yusufjon Dadajonov, Uzog Mahmudov and Yashin Hakkulov.

Each of our young students taking «Nay» lessons should enjoy the lives of the above-mentioned masters and the enchanting melodies they played.

Famous flutists currently serving: Mirza Toyirov, Halimjon Jorayev, Shukrullo Akhmadjonov, Akhmadjon Sobirov, Abdulahad Ergashev, Ilhomjon Javdotov, Halimjon Sharipov, Mansur Jomurodov and others.

Surnay.

The appearance of the «Surnay» also dates back to the centuries before our era. At the end of the 9th century, the local feudal dynasty of the Samonites managed to unify a large part of Central Asia. The capital of the state, Bukhara, has become a major cultural center. Even at that time, there was solo nawaz and ensemble music performance. The music played during the solemn ceremonies of courtiers had a special place. Usually, the ensemble is formed by the joint playing of trumpets, trumpets and drums. They played the «Surnay» mainly at palace events, parties and weddings. In many cases, the «Surnay» was played together with trumpets, drums and circles.

By the 19th century, flutes, trumpets, and bolamon musical instruments took a strong place in performance practice. A number of musicologists have reached the stage of music performance. Ustaz Qurban Saadi, who is a skilled performer, and ustoz Poyan were «Surnay» and drum players.

Darvish Ali's testimony shows that even at that time, the parties in the palace did not pass without trumpets and trumpets. In the second half of the 19th century, August Fedorovich Eichhorn (born in 1844) collected Uzbek folk instruments. The Uzbeks accompanied such trumpets as skillfully accompanied a song.

Ensembles composed of four-timbered and percussion instruments, i.e. trumpets, trumpets, circles, and drums, are widely used in weddings in Tashkent, Kokan, Fergana, Andijan, Bukhara, Khorezm and other cities of Uzbekistan. They, that is, «Surnay» players, have been actively participating in the social life of the people, in public, traditional holidays and in family life.

At the moment, taking into account the capabilities of a single instrument-trumpet, Uzbek special performance programs such as "Surnay Irog'i", "Surnay Dugohi", "Surnay Qalandary", "Surnay Navosi", "Shodiyona" "Miskin" Folk tunes are very popular. Among the famous «Surnay» players are Ashurali Mahram, a neighbor of Kokand and trumpeter Akhmadjon Umurzakov, Khudoyberdi trumpeter from Khorezm.

By 1927, the number of trumpeters had increased considerably. By the second half of the 20th century, along with the development of performance in Uzbek folk instruments, interest in folk instruments also increased. Nevertheless, efforts to improve the «Surnay» class are still ongoing.

The structure of the “Surnay”.

“Surnay” is an ancient woodwind instrument widely used among the Uzbek and Tajik peoples. It also has six holes that can be closed with the fingers of the left and right hands. The seventh hole is on the lower side, and it is closed with the thumb of the left hand. The volume of the voice extends from the small octave *lya* to the second octave *mi*. Notes are written in treble clef as they are heard. Because of its loudness, the trumpet is played in the open air at various ceremonies (without a microphone). Apricot wood is used to make the trumpet, and a special reed-like blower is installed.

“Koshnay”.

The history of the appearance of the “Koshnay” goes back to the distant past. Al-Farabi described the first examples of “Koshnay” in his musical treatise. The word “Koshnay” is derived from the Persian language and means double or two flutes. Koshnay musical instruments are performed individually, accompanied by an ensemble, and accompanied by an orchestra.

At the beginning of the 19th century, Uzbek folk musical ensembles included *gijjak*, *tanbur*, *dutor*, *chang*, *rubob*, *nay*, *koshnay*, and *doyra*. The troupe consisting of 21 performers was created in 1926 by the famous statesman *Muhyiddin Koryakubov* and was directly led by him.

With the development of an applicator that allows to use the chromatic sound line and determine a certain range in the conservatory, there was a need to teach the specialty of the conservatory.

The structure of the “Koshnay”.

As for the structure of the neighbor: it consists of two reed tubes, and a special tongue is attached to them. To play the dulcimer, two pipes are blown into the same, and the corresponding seven holes in both pipes are pressed with a finger. The volume of the voice ranges from *re* in the first octave to *sol* in the second octave (some popular speakers produce sounds in the second octave *lya*, *si* even higher). It is very convenient to play the musical decorations (melisms) typical for Uzbek music in *Koshnay*. A musician who plays tunes in the “Koshnay” is known as “Koshnay’s Musician”.

Ahmadjon Umurzakov, *Ashurali Yusupov*, among the famous “Koshnay” in Uzbekistan (those who are grateful), *Matrasul Matyokubov* (born in 1958, teacher

at Urgench Music Academy, first prize winner of the second republican status performers competition), talented young people, Bahrom Sobirov (born in 1945, composer of the "Bahor" ensemble) Yoldosh Tajiyev (born in 1960), teacher in Urgench, etc.

Karnay.

Karnay belong to the group of classical wind instruments. The structure of the Karnay consists mainly of two or three parts. Its length is more than two meters, and the blowing part has a small hole at the end. In the performance of a karnay instrument, the sounds are similar to the interval of a second, and sounds formed from two different intervals.

A pure fifth or minor seventh interval above the fundamental is played on the karnay. The performance of the trumpet is mainly performed during holidays, solemn ceremonies, feasts, weddings, trumpets and drums are sometimes accompanied by a circle.

The sound of the karnay is very loud, which is probably why it calls people to gatherings during Navroz holidays and various seasonal festivals. A musician who plays tunes on a trumpet musical instrument is called a "Karnaychi".

Bulamon.

Bulamon is one of the ancient Uzbek folk instruments. The history of the appearance of this instrument goes back to ancient times. There are also assumptions that it first appeared in the ancient oasis of Khorezm in Central Asia. Because most of its performers are the people of Khorezm and their music performers. The bulamon musical instrument is also usually made of mulberry or apricot wood. They develop it thoroughly. Its shape is similar to a trumpet, but a little smaller than it, and it is not surprising that its name comes from this. Bulamon means the son of the trumpet. The length of the bulamon is 300 mm, and it is made of reeds, which is fixed in the upper part (tongue), prepared and cut in the shape of P. There are eight holes in the bag, seven of which are on the top and one on the back. The hole on the back is at the top and is closed with the thumb of the left hand. The sound line is diatonic, starting from re, re flat in the small octave and approaching three octaves.

Bulamon can be played solo, as well as in ensembles and orchestras. On the other hand, the balaban instrument is also performed in the folk music of Armenia, Georgia, and Dagestan. Just like our baby, but the name is different.

During the time of Muhammad Rahimkhan Feruz, the best musician was Yaqub "bulamonchi", his friends Muhammad Yaqub Harrat and Abdurahmonbek were

guizhakchi. These musicians are instrumentalists who made great contributions to the development of Khorezm music.

